

JUDICIAL SYSTEM: ON THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN AND JAPAN

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ABSTRACT

In this article describes and history the process of formation of the judicial system of Uzbekistan and Japan, Judicial reform in Uzbekistan, the existence of norms regarding the judicial system in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Constitution of Japan, the inadmissibility of emergency courts, some features of the judicial system. system of lower and higher courts, methods, research and analysis, their conclusions and opinions, similarities and differences in the legislation of the judiciary, issues of cooperation between them, features of the deliberative center in Japan, special uniforms for judges in Uzbekistan and Japan, terms of office of judges, Analysis of the procedure for appointing judges in Uzbekistan and Japan, as well as problems with the submission of information by chairmen of courts and judges to the relevant Council of People's Deputies at least once a year legislation to improve the judicial system current issues, research on judicial reform, and their results, issues arising in practice, proposals and recommendations for improving national legislation and science based on the experience of Japan.

INTRODUCTION

Today, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to deepen the reforms implemented in all spheres of society's life, to renew, especially to speed up the processes of democratization.

The judicial system has a centuries-old history typical of statehood in the territory of modern Uzbekistan. Court activities have long been performed by respectable people with great life experience, based on the folk culture, traditions and spiritual basis. The decisions they issued were considered free

of any doubt and binding for all. For almost thirteen centuries, there was a judge's court that followed the laws of Sharia and a big court that made decisions based on folk customs and traditions.

As for the Japanese judicial system, the Japanese judicial system in the Middle Ages was accusatory and inquisitorial in nature. The court case was initiated based on the application of a state institution or an individual. The court was not separated from the administration. The court case was considered at the defendant's place of

residence, at the uyezd office or at the nearest state institution. Jurisdiction of the case is determined by the place where the crime was committed, or by its level of importance, or by the severity of the punishment that can be imposed. The bodies of the Ministry of Justice of that time considered the investigation and court of important cases, disputes over debt recovery.

Of course, in the years before the Meiji reforms, there were judicial bodies in Japan. But the foundations for Japan's current judicial system were created during the Meiji reforms. Moreover, before the Meiji reforms, judicial power in Japan was in the hands of local governors, who performed more to strengthen and protect the power of local governors than to perform their own judicial functions. On the basis of the Law on the Organization of Courts of 1890, the judicial system of Japan was organized, local district and appellate courts were established, administrative courts were formed from appellate courts and senior court judges. In this article, all processes in the judicial system of Uzbekistan and Japan were analyzed as an object of research.

Material and methods. historical, analytical-analytical, comparative, analogical, structural-functional, modeling methods are used within this article.

MAIN PART. Articles 106 and 116 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan clearly define the foundations of judicial power and strengthen the independence of judicial power and judges [1]. Accordingly, the judiciary and judges are subject only to the law. This provision is protected by a number of guarantees in the Constitution. The structure of the judicial system and the

powers of all judicial bodies in the Republic are also defined in the basic law.

According to Article 107 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the judicial system in the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, military courts, the court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regional and Tashkent city courts, the districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. mury court, administrative courts of regions and Tashkent city, inter-district, district, city courts for civil cases, district, city courts, inter-district, district, city economic courts and inter-district administrative courts for criminal cases. The procedure for establishing courts and their operation is determined by law. It is established that it is not allowed to create emergency courts.

Research results

Today, all countries have a judicial system, and it manifests itself in different ways. However, it is necessary to analyze which judicial system is effective and concise in these countries. The judicial system was strengthened in the Constitution of all countries. As a result of the research of this article, the judicial system will be improved and suggestions will be made for the existing legislation.

In the 2021 edition of the Rule of Law Index published by the World Justice Project, Uzbekistan rose 14 places. For example, according to the index of the rule of law, Uzbekistan ranks 85th, of which the indicator "Civil justice" is 71st, the indicator "Criminal justice" is 60th. shows that it is necessary.

Table

Хуқуқ устуворлиги индексининг индикаторлари бўйича Ўзбекистонга берилган баллар таҳлили								
			Балл		Ўзгариш ↑ ↓	Ўрин		Ўзгариш ↑ ↓
			2020	2021		2020	2021*	
Хуқуқ устуворлиги индекси			0,47	0,49	↑0,02	92	78	↑14
1	Индикаторлар	Хукумат ваколатлари чекланганлиги	0,33	0,38	↑0,05	120	110	↑10
2		Коррупция мавжуд эмаслиги	0,40	0,46	↑0,06	89	63	↑26
3		Хукумат очиқлиги	0,33	0,37	↑0,04	120	112	↑8
4		Фундаментал хуқуқлар	0,41	0,44	↑0,03	110	101	↑9
5		Тартиб ва хавфсизлик	0,90	0,90	-	11	12	↓1
6		Қонунларга риоя этиш	0,44	0,44	-	96	95	↑1
7		Фуқаролик одил судлов	0,51	0,50	↓0,01	72	71	↑1
8		Жиноий одил судлов	0,44	0,45	↑0,01	66	60	↑6
* Ўзбекистоннинг ўринлари рейтингга янги киритилган мамлакатларни инобатга олмасдан кўрсатилган								

Chapter 6, Article 76 of the Japanese Constitution deals with the judicial system, which includes the Supreme Court, High Courts, District Courts, Family Courts, Courts of General Jurisdiction, Civil Cases, Administrative Cases, Criminal Cases, Juvenile Cases according to the entry of courts [2].

Also, citizen participation in the judicial process Saibanins (Lay Judges) [3], Settlement Commissioners, Labor Tribunal Commissioners, Mental Health Judges and Counselors, Technical Counselors, Valuation Commissioners, Investigative Committee Members, District and Family

Court Committees Members of the myth are set to enter.

According to Article 76 of the Constitution of Japan, no emergency court is established and no final judicial authority is given to an executive body or office. All judges are independent in the exercise of their conscience and subject only to this Constitution and laws. According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, courts may be specialized in the categories of cases in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is not allowed to establish emergency courts. Let's look at the table of the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Japanese judicial system.

Judicial system in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan

military courts

Court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city courts

Administrative Court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, administrative courts of regions and Tashkent city

interdistrict, district, city courts for civil cases

district and city courts for criminal cases

interdistrict, district, city economic courts

interdistrict administrative courts

If we analyze the above table, the Constitutional Court is at the top in the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the Japanese judicial system, the Supreme Court is the highest. In addition, unlike the Republic of Uzbekistan, they have family courts, that is, disputes arising from family relationships are heard in these courts. However, the difference is hardly noticeable in the courts. The Supreme

Economic Court previously existed in the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and as a result of the optimization of the judicial system, this court was abolished and added to the Supreme Court.

We will mention some features of the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan and compare them based on the analysis.

Three-judge courtroom (criminal case)

- 1 Judges
- 2 Court Clerk
- 3 Court Stenographer
- 4 Court Secretary
- 5 Public Prosecutor
- 6 Defense Counsel
- 7 The Accused

In Japan, a trial court hears and decides certain cases in court sessions[6]. Judges, assistant judge, court transcript, court clerk, state prosecutor, defense attorney, defendant are scheduled to participate in the trial. In addition to the chairman of the court, two judges sit next to him. In addition, close relatives of the parties and other persons related to the case will be present in the courtroom.

Court proceedings - hearing and solving certain cases at court sessions [7]. The court hearing is organized by the chairman of the court session, who determines the scope of the issue to be considered, invites the participants, explains and provides them with their rights and obligations, ensures that the claims, objections, opinions of the plaintiff, defendant, defendant, victim and others are taken into account and the evidence is checked.

There are more than 438 courts of general jurisdiction in Japan that can take people here[8]. Courts of general jurisdiction hear cases of ¥1,400,000 or less. A consultation center operates within the courts of general jurisdiction and provides legal advice to citizens through a single window.

Consultation center in a Summary Court

In order to create more favorable conditions for finding an effective solution to citizens' appeals in the field of justice, to solve the appeal on the spot and to prevent unnecessary wanderings, court chairmen and judges have been conducting mobile receptions. In mobile receptions, citizens' appeals are accepted in matters related to criminal, civil, economic and public legal relations in administrative courts [9].

Judge's badge

Judicial robes (left: for male; right: for female)

Japanese courts also have special clothes for judges. Different from our judges dress. It also includes the uniforms of special female judges. Also, the length of the clothes of Japanese judges differs from ours. That is, they are marked shorter. In addition, Judge's badge is also given to judges[10]. In this case, the judge is special.

The color of the special clothes for the judges of the republican courts is dark blue, and for the judges of the Constitutional court it is dark-cherry and the composition is determined to consist of 70% wool. A set of special clothes for judges: special clothes, sleeves and silk collar-plaster according to the individual body sizes of judges[11], can be ordered only on the basis of a judge's certificate, special clothes for judges are winter and summer, The term of use of the judge's special uniform is 2 years.

According to Article 71 of the Law on Courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a judge is elected or appointed in the prescribed manner for the first five-year term, the next ten-year term, and the indefinite term of office [4]. Also, the term of a judge's powers is calculated based on his total length of service as a judge.

The maximum age for being a judge of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is seventy years, and for judges of other courts - sixty-five years [5]. The maximum age of being a judge of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan may be extended to five years by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with his consent, and the age of a judge of other courts may be extended to five years by the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A judge has the option to retain the right to retirement in accordance with the law.

In Japan, all judges are appointed to their positions for a period of 10 years. Appointments are made by the Cabinet of Ministers, and in most courts based on a list of candidates drawn up by the Supreme Court (the Supreme Court is appointed by the Emperor). After 10 years, a judge may be reappointed, a process that continues until the statutory retirement age (65 or 70 years) [12] is reached. The Constitution provides for a number of measures aimed at increasing the authority of judges [13].

Today, the following problems are encountered in practice. In particular, according to Article 37 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Courts, the Chairman of the Court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Region, Tashkent City Court, according to Article 41 of the Inter-District, District, City Court on Civil Cases, chairman of district, city court, inter-

district, district, city economic court for criminal cases, according to article 52, the chairman of the administrative court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional, Tashkent administrative court[14], according to article 56, the chairman of the inter-district administrative court is responsible for the rights and freedoms of citizens of the court, as well as enterprises[15], on the activities of the court to protect the rights and interests of institutions and organizations protected by the law through the courts[16], as well as the rights and interests of legal entities protected by the court It is established that the respective People's Deputies[17] will provide information on their implementation activities to the Council at least once a year[18]. And this is not information, but in practice it is becoming a form of reporting. Based on this, it is necessary to cancel the norm of judges presenting information to the Council of People's Deputies at least once a year. Because in this case, the head of the executive power and the chairman of the Council of People's Deputies are, in a word, the governor.

Conclusion

Based on the above, in conclusion, as a result of this research, we saw that all aspects of the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan were analyzed, and as a result, the differences and similarities between the two countries were considered. Also, based on the experience of Japan, we will make recommendations and suggestions for solving a number of existing problems and improving the legislation in the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

First, it is necessary to further improve the principle of independence of judges and

strengthen the punishment of the article of interfering with the decision of court cases in the Criminal Code. Because today there are cases of interference in the activities of judges.

Second, due to the large number of disputes on juvenile affairs and family affairs and taking into account the complexity of cases, it is necessary to establish courts on juvenile affairs and family affairs in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Third, after appointing judges to positions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to set a trial period for a certain period of time (at least two years).

Fourth, it is necessary to establish a library of the Supreme Court for judges and provide other courts throughout the country with the necessary references for conducting court cases. A court library

operates in Japan. It has an open access collection of about 270,000 books, of which about 170,000 are Japanese and about 100,000 foreign books, and the collection is mainly for judicial administration. includes essential legal texts, such as statute books, law reports, commentaries, article collections, and journals, as well as texts from various other scholarly fields related to litigation.

Fifth, to submit information at least once a year to the relevant Council of People's Deputies on the activities of the court presidents and judges in the implementation of the court's protection of civil rights and freedoms, as well as the rights and interests of legal entities protected by law. it is necessary to completely cancel the authority.

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